

Developing Teaching Procedure based on Communicative Language Teaching Principles to Teach Speaking

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ABSTRACT: Teaching procedure can be developed to achieve a better result, which is to improve students' speaking skill. This research aims to find out whether the developed teaching procedure based on Communicative Language Teaching principles can improve students' speaking ability. This is a quasi-experimental research design that conducts a quantitative method with 30 students as the subjects. The students were tested through the speaking test before and after the treatment. The finding shows that there is a significant increase between the pre-test and post-test. The *t*-value, which is 11.221 is higher than the *t*-table, which is 2.045. Or, the sig (2-tailed) is 0.000, which is lower than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the developed teaching procedure based on CLT principles can improve students' speaking ability.

KEYWORDS: Ability, Communicative Language Teaching, Foreign Language Anxiety, Speaking, Teaching Procedure.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning process in speaking class should be interesting that can cause students active and enjoy in learning English. Because speaking is important since the success in speaking measures one's ability to carry out a conversation in a language (Nunan, 1991). Unfortunately, sometimes the students get difficulties to speak English well. Therefore, by using some techniques, methods and approaches in teaching English, the teachers can help the students improve their speaking skill.

Communicating in English needs practice step by step. Speaking is a process to convey messages or ideas from one person to others by using verbal, so that it can make things easier (Raja, 2017). However, many students still feel anxious and not confident in doing speaking activities. Students' speaking anxiety is a problem that is common in various lessons, especially English lesson.

There are some ways that can be used to increase students' speaking ability. One of them is by applying Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) principles in the teaching procedure in order that the communication approach will be easier and can be implemented to achieve maximum results especially because the use of the teaching procedure with communicative approach makes students more motivated to improve students' speaking ability. A study by Anggraini (2018) concludes that the students can improve their speaking skill through communicative language teaching technique. It is in line with a research by Molla (2018) that concludes that CLT is really recommended to use in all level of English learning. Teachers should respond positively in implementing related approach to get the most effective way in teaching speaking. However, Yasin, et al (2017) focused to investigate whether the lesson plans designed by the teacher matched the principles and methods of the CLT approach, how the teacher implemented the CLT approach for teaching speaking skills and what learning performances resulted from using CLT. The conclusion is that the students' failure was because the procedures suggested by the experts were not entirely and effectively implemented by the teacher in her teaching process.

By viewing the researches above, the researcher intended to know whether her new teaching procedure based on communicative language teaching could help the students increase their speaking skill. It was also hoped that it could build an interaction among the students and between the students and the teacher, as a facilitator.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Burns & Joyce in Torkey (2006), speaking is defined as an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information. Speaking is the most important skill of all the four language skills because individuals who learn a language are referred to as the speakers of that language (Ur, 1996). Based on the rubric of Brown (2001)

in Karlina, et al. (2020), there are five aspects of speaking. They are grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, fluency and pronunciation.

Communicative Language teaching is an approach that focuses on meaning and using language in the real situation. The first theorist behind CLT is Chomsky in 1957. As stated by Savignon (1987), the core principle of the CLT approach is to learn the language and learn to use the language, but not learn the knowledge of the language. In addition, Larsen-Freeman (2000) states that Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) makes communicative competence as the goal of language teaching and by acknowledging the interdependence of language and communication.

Communicative Language Teaching should be adopted in every EFL classes in Indonesia since it provides opportunities for the students to communicate and base the language to its context. However, the application of CLT in Indonesia is still far to achieve the communicative goals. The students are not adequately taught speaking and listening skills, and as a result, they are unable to use English outside of the classroom. Despite the fact that government has sent materials based on the CLT system, the teachers still do not fully comprehend the principles of communicative competence. It can be seen that, in addressing CLT, there are some problems, one of them is that the materials do not contain principles of CLT yet. According to Richards & Rodgers (1986:172), the principles of communicative language teaching include:

1. Learners learn a language through using it to communicate.
2. Authentic and meaningful communication should be the goal of class- room activities.
3. Fluency is an important dimension of communication. Communication involves the integration of different language skills.
4. Communication involves the integration of different language skills
5. Learning is a process of creative construction and involves trial and error.

Communicative Language Teaching emphasizes on language as a mean of communication. In CLT, the students tend to use language for doing this in purpose of communication.

Teaching procedure is steps that explain what the students should do, how they should move, whom they should be talking to, and any other details they are expected to know. Below is a developed teaching procedure that the researcher proposes based on Communicative Language Teaching principles :

Pre-activity

- Teacher does a brainstorming to students by giving a compliment to one of the students about her new style
'Lisa, you got a new hair cut ? it's so beautiful'
- Teacher starts the lesson by asking the students
'Does anyone know how to respond to this statement ?'
The respond is : Thank you, Miss
- Teacher tells what is going to be learnt today, which is 'Giving and Responding to Compliments'

Whilst-activity

- Teacher explains and gives examples of compliments by listening to native speakers and written dialogue
- Teacher gives a compliment to a student, and the student responds the compliment
- Teacher asks the students to give a compliment to the teacher, and the teacher responds the compliment
- Teacher asks one of the student to give a compliment to another student, and the student responds his/her compliment
- Teacher asks the students to make a group of 2 students and they are asked to make a dialogue about giving and responding to compliments
- Teacher asks the students voluntarily to go to the front of the class to practice their dialogue
- Teacher asks voluntarily 3 group of students to go to the front to talk each other about giving and responding compliment directly with free topic
- Teacher gives compliments to the groups
- Students respond to the teacher's compliment

Post-activity

- Teacher gives an appreciation for the students after today's learning activity

- Teacher asks the students about the difficulties that they got when giving and responding compliment, and the teacher answers by re-explaining about giving and responding compliments
- Teacher corrects the mistakes done by the students in spelling, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar without blaming the students.
- Students with the guidance of the teacher make a conclusion about the important points that arise in the new learning activity that has been conducted.

The principles of CLT are attached since the pre-activity begins. In the pre-activity, the researcher attaches principle 1, which is ‘learners learn a language through using it to communicate’. It is because before starting the materials, the researcher must give real example of a certain topic. The example relates to the students’ real life and experiences so they are able to communicate it and it reflects to the concept of CLT.

Then, in the whilst-activity, the researcher uses all of the four principles of CLT. In this activity, each student is eligible to communicate and express their knowledge about the topic. They can share their opinion each other with their partner directly. They train their skill in communication. The topic is also about the real life, so that it eases them to talk. Students get used to speak directly to their friends and their teacher. It may increase their fluency.

In the post-activity, the researcher uses principle no. 5, which is ‘learning is a process of creative construction and involves trial and error’. The researcher makes the students focus on communicating by letting each of them explain and share what they have learned directly without being too focused on the grammar, so that the fluency is hopefully increased. Students can ask any questions to the teacher so that they get the explanation clearly. It doesn’t matter if they are wrong especially in the grammar, because they can try again for the right answer guided by the teacher.

To sum up, CLT provides the students with meaningful task and material that focuses on communicative competence. Students are the center in the learning process while the teacher’s role is as a facilitator.

METHODS

This current research is a quasi-experimental design and it conducts a quantitative method. Its goal is to intently find out whether the developed teaching procedure based on communicative language teaching principles can improve students' speaking ability. The data were calculated through paired samples t-test with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Subjects for this research were one class of SMK N 1 Candipuro that consisted of 30 students. After consulting with one of the English teacher of that school, it was known that they seemed to be in the beginner level of English and still had problems in speaking English. The data analysis used inter-rater. The first rater was the researcher herself and the other was a teacher of that school. The researcher collected the data with an instrument, i.e. speaking test. The test was administered at the beginning as the pre-test and at the the end as the post-test. The instructions of both instruments were the same. The students were asked to give a compliment and the respond to their friend. It covered the aspects of speaking by Brown (2001). As cited in Karlina & Sudirman (2020), the elaboration is as follows :

Table 1. Rubric of Speaking by Brown (2001)

	Grammar	Vocabulary	Comprehension	Fluency	Pronunciation
1	Error in grammar are frequent, but speaker can be understood by a native speaker used to dealing with foreigners attempting to speak his language.	Speaking vocabulary inadequate to express anything but the most elementary needs.	Within the scope of his very limited language experience, can understand simple questions and statements if delivered with slowed speech, repetition, or paraphrase.	(No specific fluency description. Refer to other four language areas for implied level of fluency).	Error in pronunciation are frequent but can be understood by a native speaker used to dealing with foreigners attempting to speak his language.
2	Can usually handle elementary constructions quite accurately but does not have thorough or confident control of the grammar.	Has speaking vocabulary sufficient to express himself simply with some circumlocutions.	Can get the gist of most conversations of non-technical subject (i.e., topics that require not specialized knowledge).	Can handle with confidence but not with facility most social situations, including introductions and casual conversations about current events,	Accent is intelligible though often quite faulty.

			as well as work, family, and autobiographical information.		
3	Control of grammar is good. Able to speak the language with sufficient structural accuracy to participate effectively in most formal and informal conversations on practical, social, and professional topics.	Able to speak the language with sufficient vocabulary to participate effectively in most formal and informal conversations on practical, social, and professional topics. Vocabulary is broad enough that he rarely has to grope for a word.	Comprehension is quite complete at a normal rate of speech.	Can discuss particular interests of competence with reasonable ease. Rarely has to grope for word.	Errors never interfere with understanding and rarely disturb the native speaker. Accent may be obviously foreign.
4	Able to use the language accurately on all levels normally pertinent to professional needs. Errors in grammar are quite rare.	Can understand and participate in any conversations within the range of his experience with a high degree of precision of vocabulary.	Can understand any conversation within the range of his experience.	Able to use the language fluently on all levels normally pertinent to professional needs. Can participate in any conversation within the range of this experience with a high degree of fluency.	Error in pronunciation are quite rare.
5	Equivalent to the of an educated native speaker.	Speech non all levels is fully accepted by educated by educated native speakers in all its features including breadth of vocabulary and idioms, colloquialisms, and pertinent culture references.	Equivalent to that of an educated native speaker.	Has complete fluency in the language such that his speech is fully accepted by educated native speakers.	Equivalent to and fully accepted by educated native speakers.

There are 5 scales for each element in which the number 5 is the highest score. The first element is grammar. It is to evaluate the correct grammar that the students used in speaking. It's very important, because it is known that Indonesian students often speak ungrammatically. The second one is vocabulary. It is to measure how many vocabularies that the students have. The third is comprehension. It is to figure out whether the students understand what the instruction asks them to, and to make sure what they speak is according to the instruction or not. The fourth element is fluency. It is to measure how fluent they are speaking, without several pauses. The last is pronunciation. It is to measure how exact they pronounce the words and their accents are like natives or not.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The researcher calculated the data of the post-test and pre-test in the class through paired samples t-test computed to seek whether there was a significant difference in the students' speaking achievement after the students were taught through the developed teaching procedure based on communicative language teaching principles. The following tables are the result of the paired samples t-test :

Tables 2. Paired Samples T-Test

• **Paired Samples Statistics**

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Post-test	50.6000	30	11.38844	2.07924
	Pre-test	35.8667	30	8.41892	1.53708

Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Post-test & Pre-test	30	.776	.000

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Post-test - Pre-test	14.73333	7.19163	1.31301	12.04793	17.41873	11.221	29	.000

From the tables above, the post-test and the pre-test are compared. Based on the critical value of *t* for two-tailed tests, the degrees of freedom (df) which is 29 gets the *t*-table of 2.045. The *t*-value from the table above, which is 11.221, is higher than the *t*-table. Moreover, the sig (2-tailed) is 0.000. It is lower than 0.05. It can be concluded that there is a significant increase in the post-test towards the pre-test. The hypothesis (*H*₁) is then accepted. Equally, it proves that the developed teaching procedures based on Communicative Language Teaching principles can improve students' speaking ability.

The improvement of speaking skill occurred because the procedure was developed rather than using the old procedure that most of the teachers in Indonesia use. It was developed based on communicative language teaching. The difference shows that the class of the developed procedure was alive compared to the general English classes. The researcher managed to engage all the students at class to take parts in the conversations in groups and in the whole class. By developing the teaching procedure based on CLT, it can improve the students' speaking ability. It is in line with Emilia, et al (2008) who says that through CLT, the students are able to develop the communicative competence allowing them actively use the target language.

When the developed procedure was applied at class, it made the process of teaching and learning activities come alive. Moreover, the conversations that were built by the teacher and the students boosted the students' ability in speaking. It was because the researcher always asked the students with the questions that make the students answer without paying more attention to the rule of grammar. They were trained to develop their fluency.

The result was in line with a research by Rahman (2017) who argued that communicative language teaching should be adopted in every EFL classes in Indonesia since it provided opportunities for the students to communicate and based the language to its context. Mastering speaking skill is very important for the students in order to make the student able to communicate in English with other people from other countries easily especially if they want to go abroad, it is an obligation for them to be able to communicate in English since English is the first international language in countries all over the world. This is why the developed procedure was made.

When the students were asked to answer the researcher's questions about compliment, they were very enthusiastic to answer it. And when a conversation occurred among the students, the class came alive. The researcher also didn't forget to provide them a listening session about how native speakers share their compliments. It was so interesting that the students focused to imitate the utterances from the native speakers. Moreover, Bygate (2001) states that communicative approach provides the learners with an opportunity to use language for communication purposes without focusing on accuracy. It eased the students in the process of expressing their ideas.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The students went through the learning process with a developed teaching procedure based on communicative language teaching principles in one class. The new developed teaching procedure brought positive impacts in improving students' speaking ability. It sttistically proves that there is a significant difference in students' speaking achievement of the students who were taught through the developed teaching procedure if compared between the pre-test and the post-test. The principles of CLT fostered the process of learning speaking through the developed teaching procedure. Moreover, the class came alive because most of the students took parts in the conversation. Finally, they increased their achievement of speaking ability.

Teachers must apply this developed procedure at class. This is a very good choice to break down the dead class and make the class alive, because there will be many students who take parts in the conversations. Since communicative language teaching deals with communication, an increase of the speaking ability will be obtained. Also, teachers should be creative in making the class alive.

There are many strategies to make the students want to speak. Asking them directly with a question will make the students answer it without overthinking.

This research was conducted only in a certain condition of one of vocational high school namely SMK N 1 Candipuro, South Lampung, so the results of the current research cannot be generalized. But, this research could be a reference for further researchers who want to conduct a similar research.

REFERENCES

1. Anggraini. 2008 Improving Students' Speaking Skill Through CLT An Action Research. *Wanastra*: Vol X No.1, Maret 2018
2. Bygate. 2001 *Effects of Task Repetition on the Structure and Control of Oral Language*. UK: Longman.
3. Karlina & Sudirman, A. 2020. The Effect of Application Guessing Game Pic-Pow Strategy Towards Students' Speaking Mastery at the First Class of SMA Mathla'ul Anwar Menes. *JEES: Journal of English Education Studies*, 2020, Vol. 2 No. 2
4. Larsen-Freeman, D. 2000. *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching* (2nd ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.
5. Molla, N.L. 2018 Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Approach Towards Speaking Ability. *English Focus*. 2018. 2(1): 10-24
6. Nunan, D. 1991. *Language Teaching Methodology*. Prentice Hall.
7. Rahman, A. 2017 Emerging Factors of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Its Application in Indonesian English As A Foreign Language (EFL) Classrooms. *LANGKAWI*, Vol. 3 No. 2, September 2017
8. Raja, F. 2017. Anxiety Level in Students of Public Speaking: Causes and Remedies. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 4(1), 94-110
9. Richards, J., & Rodgers, T. 1986. *Approaches and Methods in Language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
10. Savignon, S. J. 1987. Communicative Language Teaching. *Theory Into Practice*, 26(4), 235–242
11. Torky, S.A.E.F. 2006. *The Effectiveness of a Task-Based Instruction Program in Developing the English Language Speaking Skills of Secondary Stage Students*. Thesis. Ain Shams University
12. Ur, P. 1996. *A course in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
13. Yasin, B., Aziz, Z.A. and Jannah, R. 2017 Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) for Teaching Speaking. *English Education Journal (EEJ)*, 8(3), 322-337, July 2017

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